

1 **Generative Artificial Intelligence: Synthetic Datasets in Dentistry**

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43 **Abstract:**

44 **Introduction:** Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, particularly Deep Learning (DL) models are
45 known to be data intensive. This has increased the demand for digital data in all domains of
46 healthcare, including dentistry. The main hindrance in the progress of AI is access to diverse
47 datasets which train DL models ensuring optimal performance, comparable to subject experts.
48 However, administration of these traditionally acquired datasets is challenging due to privacy
49 regulations and the extensive manual annotation required by subject experts. Biases such as ethical,
50 socio-economic and class imbalances are also incorporated during the curation of these datasets,
51 limiting their overall generalizability. These challenges prevent their accrual at a larger scale for
52 training DL models.

53 **Methods:** Generative AI techniques can be useful in the production of Synthetic Datasets (SDs)
54 that can overcome issues affecting traditionally acquired datasets. Variational autoencoders,
55 generative adversarial networks and diffusion models have been used to generate SDs. The
56 following text is a review of these generative AI techniques and their operations. It discusses the
57 chances of SDs and challenges with potential solutions which will improve the understanding of
58 healthcare professionals working in AI research.

59 **Conclusion:**

60 Synthetic data customized to the need of researchers can be produced to train robust AI models.
61 These models, having been trained on such a diverse dataset will be applicable for dissemination
62 across countries. However, there is a need for the limitations associated with SDs to be better
63 understood, and attempts made to overcome those concerns prior to their widespread use.

64 **Keywords:** Artificial Intelligence, Dataset, Natural Language Processing, Biases, Healthcare
65 Industry, Big Data, Healthcare Research, Patient Data Privacy

66 **Introduction:**

67 Digitization of healthcare has enabled Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods to integrate big data for
68 effective patient management ¹. AI models particularly deep learning algorithms such as
69 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), vision transformers, and Large Language Models
70 (LLMs) require large amounts of training data to achieve acceptable performances ²⁻⁵. This has
71 increased the demand of digital data in all domains of healthcare, including dentistry ⁶. Healthcare
72 data available for training AI models includes Electronic Health Records (EHRs), radiographs,
73 clinical photographs, etc ¹. This extensive patient data can be curated to form large-scale datasets
74 for training AI on healthcare-related problems.

75 However, some pertinent concerns prevail with AI models trained on these ‘traditionally acquired’
76 datasets. An obvious hurdle is that of patient privacy that makes dataset acquisition difficult for
77 researchers ⁷. Other problems are those of representation of populations; due to unavailability of
78 widespread data, some communities may remain under-represented. AI models trained on such
79 datasets are not generalizable on the global population. For example, a widely used AI algorithm
80 in healthcare underestimated the treatment needs of African Americans and failed to triage them
81 for necessary care due to lack of sufficient data instances ⁸. Another facial recognition software
82 was biased towards Caucasians and failed to identify dark-skinned individuals ⁹. Moreover,
83 healthcare data is in a constant state of ‘shift’ due to changes in medical practices as well as patient
84 behavior requiring constant upgrade of data to ensure the real-time applicability of an AI model
85 trained on this information ¹⁰. Therefore, there is a need for dynamic and representative datasets
86 to ensure universal applicability of AI models ¹¹.

87 One possible solution is the production of ‘synthetic’ heterogeneous datasets by using generative
88 AI ¹². Recently, interest in generative AI has amplified since the advent of LLMs such as ChatGPT

89 (OpenAI) and diffusion models such as DALL-E (OpenAI) and Midjourney (Midjourney Inc.)⁵
90 ^{13,14}. If translated into healthcare, this technique holds great promise for overcoming challenges
91 associated with the need for diverse and inclusive datasets without privacy concerns¹⁵. Generative
92 AI techniques can be streamlined into research to develop broad-ranging Synthetic Datasets (SDs)
93 that simulate real-life healthcare data. These generative models learn patterns from the input
94 (training data) and produce synthetic data as outputs¹⁵.

95 The following narrative describes challenges faced by researchers in the curation of traditional
96 datasets. It further explains the mechanism of some generative AI techniques that can be used to
97 generate SDs.

98 **Challenges of ‘traditionally acquired’ datasets:**

99 **1. Data privacy and ethical concerns:**

100 On an organizational level, healthcare data is costly and is associated with a deep-seated resistance
101 to data sharing between institutions since it is considered hospital property². Data transfer
102 agreements, including the Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 in the United States, has set
103 strict regulations to ensure patient confidentiality¹⁵. These regulations make it exceedingly
104 difficult for researchers to access medical data, leading to a lack of diversity in the currently
105 available datasets. Additionally, erasing the metadata associated with medical images does not
106 ensure patient privacy, which can still be compromised, making it challenging to share data across
107 institutions¹⁵.

108 **2. Data annotation:**

109 The curation and annotation of large-scale datasets is a time-consuming and resource-intensive
110 task³. It requires subject experts to manually label all features in an image, spending valuable time
111 developing the dataset. This cumbersome task prevents researchers from investing time

112 performing experiments ^{3, 11}. Moreover, errors can be incorporated into these labels, decreasing
113 accuracy of the AI model trained on this data. Generation of synthetic and fully annotated data can
114 potentially eliminate laborious annotations, accelerating AI research.

115 **3. Biases:**

116 Bias may be quantified as the differential impact of a healthcare process on a particular subgroup
117 ¹⁶. AI may be considered free of human bias due to its self-learning nature, however biases in AI
118 development can be introduced at any stage of the algorithm development process ¹⁶. This is due
119 to the black box nature of contemporary AI systems ¹⁷.

120 Due to the upsurge of AI in developed countries, the datasets produced are not representative of
121 the global population, which have led to data-driven biases such as those of socioeconomic
122 standing and ethnicity ¹⁸. Another type of bias that may be incorporated into traditional datasets is
123 due to the acquisition of images from a specific machine. All images in this dataset have distinct
124 dimensions limiting variations in data required to develop a generalizable AI model. Moreover,
125 the presence of ‘class imbalances’ in datasets, such as the lack of sufficient examples of a rare
126 disease in dataset gathered from a population, inculcating sample selection bias that also hinder
127 the real-life applicability of AI models trained on these datasets ¹⁸. It is therefore imperative that
128 data from as many countries as possible be included.

129 **Generative AI techniques:**

130 There are various AI techniques for generating synthetic datasets. The mechanisms of more
131 common ones have been described in the following text.

132 1. Variational Autoencoders (VAEs):

133 VAEs are an advanced version of a deep generative model known as Auto Encoder (AE), that can
134 learn complicated patterns in training data. AE consists of two parts: an ‘encoder’ and a ‘decoder’;

135 the encoder takes high-dimensional input data, such as an image or a text sequence, and maps it to
136 a lower-dimensional representation known as 'latent space'. This space is a compressed version of
137 original input data, capturing the most relevant features in a simplified form for easier processing
138 ^{19, 20}. The decoder then employs this compressed latent space data and reconstructs it back to its
139 original form. However, AEs are deterministic, meaning that no 'new' data is generated, and these
140 can only reconstruct the original data ^{19, 20} (figure 1 a & b).

141 VAEs extend the concept of AEs by introducing statistical techniques, such as probability
142 distributions (a mean value and standard deviation), into the latent space. This probabilistic
143 approach allows VAEs to learn a range of possible values for each encoded input, meaning that
144 VAEs can reconstruct original data by creating new and similar data points of the original data,
145 leading to the production of synthetic data ^{21, 22}.

146 VAEs have been used in medicine and dentistry, enabling the generation of realistic medical
147 images and health records, improving lung sound classification, and overcoming data limitations
148 in medical imaging analysis. Their effectiveness in generating clinical sounds, images and realistic
149 EHRs shows promise in advancing data-driven medical care delivery ²³.

150 2. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs):

151 GANs comprise of two neural networks: a 'generator' and a 'discriminator' ^{20, 24}. The generator
152 uses random noise (gaussian) and produces an image which closely resembles the real images. The
153 discriminator receives the images with the task of distinguishing between 'real' and 'fake' ones ²⁰.

154 As the name suggests, these models are trained in an adversarial way; the generator is trained to
155 generate images closely mimicking real images to mislead the discriminator. On the other hand,
156 the discriminator is educated to progressively improve at distinguishing real images from the false
157 ones. The generator improves at generating realistic images as the training goes on, while the

158 discriminator improves at detecting fraudulent ones. In this concept there is always a winner and
159 loser in which the loser will update its internal parameters for the next iteration, thus ensuring
160 constant improvement (figure 1 c).

161 Researchers have used GANs to generate two-dimensional cephalograms from Cone Beam
162 Computed Tomography (CBCT) and improve landmark detection ²⁵. GANs have been utilized to
163 generate highly realistic intraoral images which experienced pediatric dentists were unable to
164 distinguish them as either fake or real ²⁶.

165 3. Diffusion Models:

166 Recently, diffusion models have gained popularity as generative AI that can yield superior results
167 compared to GANs and VAEs ²⁷ (figure 1 d). These models create new data using a two-step
168 process: the ‘forward pass’ (encoder) and the ‘backward pass’ (decoder). During the forward pass,
169 noise (gaussian) is progressively added to the data (pictures, radiographs, etc) in an iterative
170 manner. This means that at each step of the process, noise is introduced into the image. In the
171 backward pass, the model reverses this process and attempts to remove noise from the image. This
172 allows the model to learn the relationship between different pixels in an image. Thus, the models
173 ‘corrupt’ training image by adding noise and then learn to recover the data during the denoising
174 process. The model can therefore be trained to generate new images using prompts ²⁷.

175 In healthcare research, diffusion models have been utilized to generate realistic chest X-ray,
176 Magnetic Resonance Imaging and histology images ²⁸.

177 **Chances of SDs:**

178 SDs can add further value to the following healthcare domains.

179 1. Research

180 Since the performance of an AI model is dependent on the amount and variation of data used for
181 training, SDs can lead to the development of robust models³. Traditionally, data augmentation is
182 carried out by simple modifications to the training dataset such as flipping, rotation, translation,
183 etc but these alterations add limited new features to the dataset²⁹. The generation of synthetic
184 images allows for augmentation at a wider scale by adding images of greater variance to the
185 dataset.

186 The potential of generative AI is being considered for producing new types of data for researchers
187 to conduct experiments. For example, in drug discovery, where AI can be utilized to generate
188 candidate molecules for pharmaceuticals to create new compounds for lab testing³⁰. Synthetic
189 Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) can be used where specific rare examples of disease
190 can be generated and purposefully combined into SDs to include all possible features of data³¹.
191 SMOTE can also potentially mitigate ‘shifts’ in data, by adding synthetic examples of new
192 emerging data features within populations. This will ensure that the SDs remain applicable and
193 generalizable with the constantly changing medical practices³².

194 2. Education

195 SDs can also be developed for creating simulations for training dental and medical students¹.
196 These simulations can be customized to the individual needs of every student, helping train them
197 in their areas of deficiency³³. With the current pace of advancements in generative AI, a virtual
198 instructor with generated characters seems likely in the near future. Educational chatbots specific
199 to different fields of study are already emerging, with sure improvements in the future.

200 **Challenges of SDs:**

201 The extensive use of SDs is not without its shortcomings which may have a negative impact on
202 patient care.

203 1. Confidentiality

204 Due to its ability to learn the original distribution of data, generative AI may still lead to patient
205 re-identification by associating the image with information such as patient visit date and time of
206 exposure ²³. Therefore to mitigate this issue, any patient identifiers need to be manually removed
207 from the training images to prevent ‘privacy leakage’ ²³.

208 2. Metrics for ‘syntheticism’

209 There is a lack of research relating to the evaluation of these generative AI models. Standardized
210 evaluation metrics are needed to determine the level of syntheticism of SDs ³⁴. The images should
211 be ‘synthetic’ enough to avoid any resemblance to real images, and ‘realistic’ enough to be
212 applicable to real-world scenarios. Before SDs can be employed for training AI, its realism needs
213 to be determined by a subject expert ^{1, 35}. Moreover, it has been shown that synthetic images of
214 lower resolution are difficult to distinguish and exhibit more ‘realism’ than those with higher
215 resolutions ²⁶. One such metric for evaluating the realism of SDs include ‘fidelity’ that measures
216 the structural similarity between original and synthetic images ³⁶.

217 3. Biases

218 Despite the advantage of reduced biases associated with SDs, generative models can still retain
219 some of the biases ³⁶. Since humans are involved in the production of synthetic data, the inherent
220 risk of incorporating human bias remains an area of concern. Similar to ‘provider bias’ where a
221 physician may be prejudiced against a certain racial group for example, these biases invariably
222 translate into AI models ³⁶. If these biases are not addressed at an early stage of AI development,
223 it can lead to inaccurate results that are not representative of the population ³⁷. For the elimination
224 of biases, it is crucial to identify all possible biases as well as the cause of their incorporation
225 during the ‘AI cycle’ (figure 2). One method includes the bioethical analysis of AI cycles from the

226 initial developmental stages through deployment ³⁶. The identification and mitigation of biases
227 improves ‘AI fairness’; this implies equal performance of the AI model across all subgroups in a
228 population ³⁸. Some measures to ensure clinical AI fairness include panels of AI researchers,
229 clinicians, and ethicists proactively overseeing the process of dataset curation and model training
230 to ensure a clinically fair AI model ³². Detailed discussions on mitigation of biases in AI is beyond
231 the scope of this paper and can be found elsewhere ³⁶.

232 4. False synthetic data

233 Generative AI can purposefully be used for the production of false data also known as ‘deepfakes’
234 ³⁹. These synthetically altered images are a threatening advancement in AI that can potentially
235 cause harm to individuals as well as industries ³⁹.

236 Hallucination is a pertinent issue that has surfaced with the widespread use of generative AI. This
237 refers to the phenomenon of production of synthetic images with factual errors, much like the
238 incorrect information that has been produced by ChatGPT ³⁹. Since synthetic healthcare data is
239 representative of authentic data that is used to treat humans, the incorporation of data with errors
240 such as incorrect anatomy or false illustration of disease can be detrimental. Further research is
241 required to better understand the implication of hallucinations and deepfakes in synthetic medical
242 and dental data. The reliability of SDs is difficult to determine as there are no evaluation metrics
243 so far since this aspect of AI is still under development. One possible way to determine the
244 robustness of SDs is to involve subject level experts such as doctors for medical images, to validate
245 the accuracy of the images before utilization.

246 **Conclusion:**

247 VAEs, GANs and diffusion models have been utilized in healthcare research to generate SDs.
248 Synthetic data customized to the need of researchers can be produced to train robust AI models.

249 These models, having been trained on such a diverse dataset will be applicable for dissemination
250 across countries. However, there is a need for the limitations associated with SDs to be better
251 understood, and attempts made to overcome those concerns prior to their widespread use. Of
252 greater importance is the need for AI governance to ensure that generative AI is being implemented
253 in a way that is beneficial to the society⁴⁰. Transparency in AI development and adherence to strict
254 standards is a prerequisite for this technology to make a noticeable impact in healthcare settings.

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270 **Figure Legends:**

271 **Figure 1(a):** Auto Encoder – A high-dimensional input image processed through the latent space
272 with deterministic variables to produce a low-dimensional output image.

273 **Figure 1(b):** Variational Autoencoder – A high-dimensional input image processed through the
274 latent space with probabilistic variables to produce a ‘new’ high-dimensional output image.

275 **Figure 1(c):** The workflow of a generative adversarial network, showing the working of generator
276 and discriminator models. Incorrect predictions lead to the generator and discriminator model
277 adjusting their internal parameters to improve their performance after each iteration.

278 **Figure 1(d):** The forward and backward passes of a diffusion model which uses gaussian noise to
279 generate a ‘new’ image.

280 **Figure 2:** Challenges and biases in the entire AI cycle. Denoted are the aspects that can be
281 managed with the use of SDs.

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369 Figure 1

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371 Figure 2